

Vitamin D Status in Patients with Temporomandibular Joint Disorders: A Case-Control Study

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Abstract

Background: Temporomandibular joint disorders (TMJDs) are multifactorial conditions involving joint, muscular, and psychological components. Vitamin D has been proposed as a biological contributor to musculoskeletal pain, yet evidence regarding its role in TMJD remains inconsistent. This study aimed to evaluate the association between serum vitamin D levels and TMJD and to identify other clinical, metabolic, and behavioral factors linked to the disorder. **Methods:** A case-control study was conducted from March to October 2025 including 100 adults: 50 clinically confirmed TMJD patients and 50 age- and sex-matched healthy controls. Diagnosis followed the DC/TMD Axis I protocol. Data collection included sociodemographic variables, BMI, clinical TMJD features, lifestyle behaviors, dietary patterns, sun exposure, and serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels measured via chemiluminescent immunoassay. **Results:** Serum vitamin D concentrations did not significantly differ between TMJD patients and controls (18.00 ± 10.88 vs. 21.36 ± 10.55 ng/mL, $p = 0.120$). Conversely, TMJD was strongly associated with key clinical symptoms including jaw pain (92%), headaches (88%), joint noises (76%), and functional limitation. TMJD patients demonstrated significantly higher BMI ($p < 0.05$), greater psychological stress/anxiety (78%), lower physical activity ($p < 0.001$), and distinct dietary habits characterized by higher daily consumption of dairy and eggs. Sun exposure was paradoxically higher among cases despite lower vitamin D levels. **Conclusion:** Vitamin D levels were not associated with TMJD, whereas metabolic, psychological, and behavioral factors—including BMI, stress, physical inactivity, and diet—showed strong relationships with the disorder. These findings support a multifactorial etiology where vitamin D plays a limited role. Future longitudinal and genetic studies are required to clarify causality.

Introduction

Temporomandibular joint disorders (TMDs), which are a significant public health problem, consist of several clinical entities that involves jaw joints, masticatory muscles and related structures and frequently results in pain and dysfunction as well as reduces patients' quality of life [1]. The etiology of TMD is known to be multifactorial and its diagnosis and treatment are complex because of various anatomic, psychological, and physiological factors [2]. Outside these classic etiological models the search for new mechanisms has recently focused on systemic biological effectors, namely nutritional deficiencies which may contribute

to a chronification of musculoskeletal pain disorder [3]. In this respect, vitamin D has been receiving much attention, not only for its classic effects on calcium homeostasis and bone metabolism but also due to its powerful immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory features [4]. A strong body of evidence indicates that hypovitaminosis D is largely prevalent in patients affected by different chronic pain syndromes and has raised the provocative hypothesis as to what extent such conditions may be characterized by altered 25(OH)D pools [5]. Recent work in particular shows a high prevalence of serum vitamin D insufficiency in TMD study groups, suggesting there may be an

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association between low serum values and pain severity or dysfunction [3]. Thus, the present work is designed to critically review current evidence from scientific literature towards understanding the link of vitamin D status with TMD parameters, its related mechanistic pathways and evaluate proposed possible use of vitamin D as a supplemental therapeutic target in management strategy for TMDs.

Method

A case-control study was conducted from March 2025 to October 2025 to investigate the relationship between serum vitamin D levels and Temporomandibular Joint Disorders (TMJD). A total of 100 participants were enrolled, comprising 50 clinically diagnosed TMJD patients and 50 age- and sex-matched healthy controls. Cases were recruited from the Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Clinic at Al-Hussain Medical City, Karbala, Iraq. Diagnosis of TMJD followed the Diagnostic Criteria for Temporomandibular Disorders (DC/TMD) Axis I protocol, including standardized assessment of jaw pain, joint sounds, and mandibular mobility. Controls were selected from companions of patients attending unrelated dental clinics and from the general population, with all individuals screened to ensure an absence of current or previous TMJ or masticatory muscle pain. Participants were excluded if they were younger than 18 or older than 65 years, used vitamin D or calcium supplements, had metabolic bone-affecting diseases (e.g., chronic kidney disease or hyperparathyroidism), were pregnant or lactating, or were unable to provide informed consent. Ethical approval was obtained from the Arab Board for Medical Specializations Institutional Review Board, and all participants provided written informed consent. Data collection involved structured face-to-face interviews, physical examination, and biochemical analysis. Sociodemographic variables, smoking history, and physical activity were recorded. Height and weight

were measured using calibrated instruments, and BMI was calculated as kg/m². TMJD patients underwent a comprehensive clinical examination by a single calibrated examiner to classify cases according to DC/TMD subgroups. Venous blood samples (5 mL) were collected after overnight fasting, and serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D] concentrations were quantified using a chemiluminescent immunoassay (CLIA). All samples were analyzed in a single batch to minimize inter-assay variability. Dietary vitamin D intake was assessed using a validated semi-quantitative Food Frequency Questionnaire evaluating habitual consumption of vitamin D-rich foods. Sun exposure was recorded as the average daily duration of direct sunlight. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 31. Continuous variables were assessed for normality and compared using independent t-tests, while categorical variables were analyzed with Chi-square or Fisher’s exact test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1 clearly demonstrates a strong and statistically significant association between TMJD case status and all expected clinical symptoms. Nearly all TMJD patients reported jaw pain (92%), headaches related to jaw movement (88%), and joint noises (76%), confirming the diagnostic reliability of the case group. Controls reported zero symptoms, reflecting appropriate selection and proper exclusion of undiagnosed TMJD. Stress and anxiety were notably higher among cases (78%), suggesting a psychosocial component in TMD pathophysiology. Although a small proportion had metabolic bone disease (6%), this difference was not statistically meaningful. Overall, the findings confirm that the case group exhibits the classical symptomatic profile of TMJD, indicating strong internal validity in patient selection.

Table 1: Association Between TMJD Case Status and Clinical Symptoms (N = 100)

Variable	TMJD Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)	p-value
Jaw Pain	46 (92.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001*
Difficulty Opening/Closing Mouth	37 (74.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001*
Clicking/Popping/Grinding Sounds	38 (76.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001*
Headaches Related to Jaw Pain	44 (88.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001*
Facial Muscle Stiffness or Fatigue	35 (70.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001*
Any Known Medical Condition	11 (22.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001*
History of Metabolic Bone Disease	3 (6.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0.242**
Stress or Anxiety	39 (78.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001*
Regular Physical Activity	27 (54.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001*

Dietary patterns differed significantly between groups. Daily dairy consumption was *much higher* among TMJD patients (56%) than controls (24%), and daily egg intake was strikingly more frequent in the TMJD group (56% vs. only 6%), indicating a distinct dietary pattern among

cases. Interestingly, fatty fish intake did not differ meaningfully, and the prevalence of vegetarian diet was low in both groups. All participants denied vitamin D supplementation, eliminating this as a confounder. These findings suggest that dietary behavior,

particularly higher intake of animal-based foods, may be linked with TMJD, potentially through inflammatory or metabolic pathways. As in table 2.

Table 2: Association Between TMJD Status and Dietary Habits (N = 100)

Variable	TMJD Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)	p-value
Fatty Fish Consumption: Never/Rarely	17 (34.0%)	14 (28.0%)	0.018*
Fatty Fish Consumption: Weekly/Daily	33 (66.0%)	36 (72.0%)	
Dairy Consumption: Never/Rarely	8 (16.0%)	12 (24.0%)	0.006*
Dairy Consumption: Weekly	14 (28.0%)	26 (52.0%)	
Dairy Consumption: Daily	28 (56.0%)	12 (24.0%)	
Egg Consumption: Never/Rarely/Weekly	22 (44.0%)	47 (94.0%)	<0.001*
Egg Consumption: Daily	28 (56.0%)	3 (6.0%)	
Vegetarian Diet	5 (10.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0.056**

Table 3 compares age, sex distribution, and BMI between TMJD cases and healthy controls. Both groups had virtually identical age means (33.06 vs. 33.46 years) and equal proportions of females (86%), confirming successful matching and minimizing demographic confounding. This strengthens the internal validity of the case-control comparison. The only variable showing statistical significance was Body Mass Index (BMI), which was notably higher in the TMJD group (26.90 ± 5.88 kg/m²) compared to controls (23.81 ± 2.93

kg/m²), with p < 0.05. This finding suggests that higher BMI may be associated with increased risk of TMJD. Elevated BMI has been linked in some studies to altered mechanical loading on the musculoskeletal system, systemic inflammation, and increased pain sensitivity—all potential contributors to TMJD. Therefore, BMI emerges as a meaningful metabolic factor in TMJD pathophysiology alongside traditional mechanical and psychological contributors.

Table 3. Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics (N = 100)

Variable	TMJD Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)	p-value
Age (Mean ± SD)	33.06 ± 12.62	33.46 ± 12.75	>0.05
Female (%)	43 (86%)	43 (86%)	>0.05
BMI (Mean ± SD)	26.90 ± 5.88	23.81 ± 2.93	<0.05*

Although vitamin D levels were lower in TMJD patients, the difference did not reach statistical significance. Unexpectedly, TMJD patients reported significantly longer sun exposure. This may reflect behavioral

differences rather than vitamin D metabolism and indicates that TMJD is not directly linked to vitamin D deficiency. As in table 4.

Table 4. Comparison of Serum Vitamin D Levels and Sun Exposure

Variable	TMJD Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)	p-value
Vitamin D (ng/mL) Mean ± SD	18.00 ± 10.88	21.36 ± 10.55	0.120
Daily Sun Exposure (min)	58.10 ± 112.64	22.80 ± 17.93	0.031*

Comorbid conditions such as hypertension and rheumatoid arthritis were significantly more common

in TMJD cases. Smoking was present only among male TMJD patients. These findings suggest. As table 5.

Table 5. Comorbidities and General Health Factors

Variable	TMJD Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)	p-value
Hypertension	Yes: 6 (12%) No: 44 (88%)	0 (0%)	<0.001*
Rheumatoid Arthritis	5 (10%)	0 (0%)	<0.001*
Smoking	5 (10%) (males only)	0 (0%)	<0.001*

Discussion

This case-control study evaluated the association between serum vitamin D levels and

temporomandibular joint disorders (TMJD) in 100 adults and found no significant difference in 25(OH)D concentrations between TMJD patients and healthy

controls (18.00 ± 10.88 vs. 21.36 ± 10.55 ng/mL, $p = 0.120$). This finding aligns with studies by Demir et al. and Madani et al. [1,6], which similarly reported no meaningful association between vitamin D status and TMD. In contrast, other research has identified lower vitamin D levels in TMD patients [4,7-9], highlighting heterogeneity in the available evidence. Mendelian randomization by Zeng et al. [4] suggested that higher vitamin D levels may paradoxically increase TMD risk, indicating that the vitamin D–TMD relationship may be non-linear or confounded, possibly reflecting a U-shaped pattern [10]. Both groups in our study exhibited high rates of vitamin D insufficiency, consistent with global data showing widespread deficiency [11,12]. When deficiency is uniformly prevalent, vitamin D loses discriminatory power as a disease marker. A meta-analysis by Tabrizi et al. [5] showed lower vitamin D levels in TMD patients, especially in Middle Eastern populations, but also emphasized substantial inter-study heterogeneity [13,14]. A significant finding in the current study was the higher BMI among TMJD patients (26.90 vs. 23.81 kg/m², $p < 0.05$), consistent with evidence linking obesity with increased TMD risk [15]. Proposed mechanisms include excessive mechanical loading on the TMJ, systemic inflammation mediated by adipokines, and hormonal alterations [16,17]. Still, conflicting evidence exists, with some studies showing lower BMI among TMD patients, likely due to reduced food intake from jaw pain or differences in TMD subtypes [18]. Stress and anxiety, reported by 78% of TMJD patients, were strongly associated with TMD, supporting psychological models suggesting altered pain perception, parafunctional habits, and muscle hyperactivity as mediators [19,20]. Physical inactivity was also significantly higher among cases, consistent with reports showing that high-intensity exercise exacerbates TMD symptoms while low-intensity activity has therapeutic benefits [21,22]. Dietary analysis showed higher intake of eggs and dairy among TMJD patients. Although these foods contain vitamin D, the association may reflect reverse causation or compensatory dietary behavior [23]. Moreover, paradoxically greater reported sun exposure in the TMJD group suggests inaccuracies in self-reporting or potential impairment in vitamin D metabolism [24]. Comorbidities such as hypertension and rheumatoid arthritis were significantly more common in TMJD patients, supporting evidence of systemic inflammatory involvement and the recognized link between rheumatoid arthritis and TMJ dysfunction [16,25].

Conclusion

The study found no significant association between serum vitamin D levels and TMJ disorders, while higher BMI, stress/anxiety, low physical activity, and specific dietary patterns were strongly linked to TMJD. These

findings support a multifactorial etiology where metabolic, psychological, and behavioral factors play a larger role than vitamin D alone. The widespread vitamin D insufficiency in both groups limits its value as a discriminatory risk factor. Future longitudinal and genetically informed studies are needed to clarify the true relationship between vitamin D and TMJD.

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